

Measuring methane emission

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Recent estimates of annual global CH₄ emission from ricefields range from 20 to 100 Tg, with a best estimate of 60 Tg. Global and regional estimates vary greatly, with assumptions based on the understanding of processes and data currently available. Reducing these uncertainties and predicting future emission trends — as well as developing mitigation technologies that do not negate gains in rice production — require information about processes and geographic distribution of factors controlling CH₄ fluxes in ricefields.

Methane fluxes from ricefields are highly variable, with distinct diel and seasonal patterns. Continuous measurements are essential to monitor and evaluate CH₄ fluxes. We employed a system that allows continuous and simultaneous measurements at 16 plots for an entire growing season. Soil at the experimental site is an Aquandic Epiaqualf (Guadalupe clay, pH 6.4, organic C 1.57%, total N 0.174%, CEC 37.3 meq/100 g).

Flooding and puddling wetland ricefields render the soil an ideal growth medium by buffering it and increasing nutrient availability. Flooding drastically reduces the oxygen supply, thereby inducing anaerobic fermentation of organic matter in the soil. A pH of around 7 and a redox potential below -150 mV favor methanogenesis. In the irrigated wetland soil monitored, we found a constant pH of 7 soon after flooding soil and solution Eh varied from 0 to -100mV (corresponding to a soil Eh of -150 to -250mV) and soil temperature ranged from 26 to 30 °C.

Integrating continuous CH₄ flux measurements with respective climate, soil, and crop data provides the essential base to identify controlling factors and processes that are required to predict future emission trends and to develop mitigation technologies. ■

Effect of rice cultivars on methane emission

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Rice plants play an important role in the flux of CH₄. Up to 90% of the CH₄ released from ricefields into the atmosphere is emitted through the rice plant. Well-developed intracellular air spaces (aerenchyma) in leaf blades, leaf sheaths, culm, and roots provide an efficient gas exchange medium between the atmosphere and the anaerobic soil (see figure).

Atmospheric oxygen needed for respiration is supplied through the aerenchyma to the roots. Gases formed in the soil, such as CH₄, diffuse from the reduced soil through the aerenchyma to the atmosphere. Production and transport of CH₄ to the atmosphere appear to depend on the rice plant's properties. The rice plant does not only mediate CH₄ flux; root exudates and degrading roots are important sources of CH₄, especially at later growth stages.

The flux of gases in the aerenchyma depends on concentration gradients and diffusion coefficients of roots and the internal structure of the aerenchyma. Tillers/m², root mass, rooting pattern, total biomass, and metabolic activity influence gas fluxes. These traits and related emission rates vary widely among cultivars and rice crops in the field, making it possible for breeders to develop rices with low CH₄ emission potential.

Large cultivar differences in emission rates have been reported (see table). We found that traditional variety Dular emitted about 30% more CH₄ per day than did the new plant type IR65597. The traditional variety has more tillers and longer roots, and these appear to enhance CH₄ emission. To compare the emission potential of rice under field conditions, actual crop parameters, such as tillers/m² for optimum yield, are as important as characteristics of the cultivar itself. Keeping the number of productive tillers/m² and eliminating unproductive tillers while developing new plant types

will result in lower field emission potentials even if other CH₄-related traits remain the same. ■

Intersection of shoot and root aerenchyma, which highly affects the diffusion of gases. Root and shoot aerenchyma are separated by cell layers (Butterbach-Bahl 1992).

W = root, AB = aerenchyma of culm, BS = culm, Aw = aerenchyma of root.

Tillers/m² at optimum crop development and methane emission of 3 cultivars.

Cultivar	Tillers/m ² (no.)		Methane emission (g)	
	Total	Productive	per tiller	per g biomass
New plant type	300	300	12	3
Improved variety	1000	600	5	4
Traditional	1200	500	13	8